

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-09

Semi-circular
rainwater and runoff
micro-catchments
for tree crops

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//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Rainwater micro-catchments

INPUTS

small earthworks; rainfall and surface runoff

OUTPUTS

Localized root-zone recharge

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 8

CONTEXT & SCALE

Arid and semi-arid regions; perennial cropping systems where intensive terrain modification is not feasible; Tree-by-tree or row-scale

KEY BENEFITS

Increased water retention and infiltration; enhanced root-zone moisture and salt leaching; reduced irrigation demand and improved water-use efficiency; improved drought resilience; cost-effective and easily replicable

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Proper site-specific design depending on crop canopy, soil, slope, and rainfall regime; not ideal on heavy clay with drainage issues.

CATEGORY

Rainwater

//02. WHAT IT IS

Micro-catchments are small basins or shaped areas that direct rainfall toward individual trees or rows, increasing effective precipitation at the root zone. The semi-circular ('Half-moon') shaped micro-catchment rainwater harvesting technique is

traditionally used in arid and semi-arid regions and has been applied for centuries in Africa and the Middle East to capture runoff, improve infiltration, and support evenly distributed vegetation growth.

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//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In semi-arid regions, like the Mediterranean, agricultural systems are increasingly exposed to prolonged droughts, rising temperatures, and irregular rainfall patterns driven by climate change and land degradation. When rainfall does occur, it often falls in short, intense events. Dry, degraded soils are unable to absorb the water efficiently, leading to rapid runoff and evaporation rather than effective soil recharge resulting in poor root-zone moisture availability and increased irrigation dependency. This type of context, is soil salinization. It

occurs when irrigation or shallow groundwater brings dissolved salts into the root zone and, because evaporation (and plant uptake) exceeds rainfall and drainage, the water leaves but the salts remain and accumulate over time. By capturing rainfall and reducing runoff, half-moon systems enhance infiltration, improve soil moisture storage and fertility, facilitate leaching of accumulated salts from the root zone, and increase the climate resilience of perennial crops.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

This solution consists of shallow, semi-circular earthen micro-basins constructed with their opening facing upslope, perpendicular to the direction of surface water flow. Runoff is slowed, captured in the basin so that it can gradually infiltrate the soil and be available to plants over a longer period and in larger quantities.

For the solution to be installed, semi-circular micro-basins (“half-moons”) are constructed around every individual tree to capture and retain rainfall and surface runoff, mimicking natural concave landforms where water accumulates. Basins are typically up to 30cm deep (on the lowest point), with a radius of approximately 3–4m depending mostly on canopy size, plant-

ing space and row width of the trees. Thus, larger configurations may be applied for bigger trees with wider planting distances. Excavated soil is gathered along the downslope edge to form a low compacted dam (up to 20cm height), which slows runoff and promotes infiltration. The system can be implemented using hand tools or light machinery and integrated with existing irrigation and fertigation systems. As a low-tech, nature-based solution, it is scalable, cost-effective, and easily replicable across (large) orchard systems in semi-arid regions. Retention volumes of up to 1.000 m³ per hectare can be achieved, which accounts for around 10mm of additionally captured rain per event.

Processes in a rainwater and runoff half-moon micro-catchments.

Note: Image generated using ChatGPT5.2, OpenAI, with the prompt “Generate a schematic overview using the text of the ‘How it Works’ factsheet section”, 2026

//05. HOW IT WORKS

During rainfall events, half-moon micro-basins capture direct precipitation and surface runoff, reducing flow velocity and thus preventing water losses. Retained water gradually infiltrates into the soil profile, increasing root-zone water availabil-

ity and supporting soil moisture storage during dry periods. By improving infiltration and soil structure, the system enhances both effective rainfall and supplemental irrigation, contributing to higher water-use efficiency.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

Once established, this low-tech solution requires minimal maintenance. Inspections after heavy rainfall are recommended to remove accumulated sediment and repair

dams if needed. Regular monitoring of soil moisture and tree performance supports system optimisation and helps ensure long-term effectiveness.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Potential risks include limited infiltration in compacted soils and overtopping during extreme rainfall events. These can be mitigated through light soil loosening and organic matter incorporation to improve infiltration, as well as by adjusting basin

size, dam height, spacing, and overflow alignment to safely manage excess runoff. Careful implementation is required in intensively rooted soils to minimise the risk of damaging the root system of the trees.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Perennial orchard systems in Mediterranean, arid and semi-arid regions facing water scarcity, high evapotranspiration, irregular rainfall and soil salinity risks, particularly where runoff losses are high and

low-tech, nature-based solutions are needed. Within the GEORGIA project, the solution is implemented at the citrus orchards of [Cyprus Phassouri Plantations Co.](#)

//09. KEYWORDS

Micro-catchment; Rainwater harvesting; Effective rainfall; Enhanced infiltration; Soil moisture retention

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

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//10. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

1. The Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) "Impact of agro-ecological techniques on soil fertility and productivity of sorghum and pearl millet in Burkina Faso". Rome, Italy. 2017.

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2. Barry, B., R. Namara, L. Hope and E. Owusu "Water harvesting technologies in the African drylands: Potential and challenges." Water International, 45(3), 235–248. 2020.

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3. W. Critchley and K. Siegert, K. "Water harvesting: A manual for the design and construction of water harvesting schemes for plant production." Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

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